

DIPLOMA

TA'LIM FIDOYILARI

RESPUBLIKA ILMIY JURNALIDA

Abdiyev Sokhibsher Ashurovich

INTERCULTURAL COMMUNICATION AND INTERNET RESOURCES IN FOREIGN
LANGUAGE LEARNING

NOMLI MAQOLASI BILAN ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN TAQDIRLANADI

Bosh muharrir:
A.A. Abdurahmonov

2023/MART

★ ★ ★ ★ ★
HONORED
MENTION
★ ★ ★ ★ ★

YOUR
SEAL